

A Simple Analytical Note on Cancer Incidence Rates within a High-Profile South Korean Observational Study

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Abstract

Background: This study examines the structural consistency of a recent South Korean observational cohort regarding post-COVID-19 vaccination oncological incidence.

Objective: To compare the internal metrics of the study cohort with official South Korean national benchmark statistics.

Methods: Comparison was conducted across three parameters: crude incidence rates, demographic distribution, and stratified incidence differences relative to 2022 cancer registry data.

Results: Findings show a -26.0% discrepancy in total incidence, a -32.5% difference in elderly population representation, and a -45.1% lower incidence in the unvaccinated control group compared to national data.

Conclusion: In light of the evidence, a selection bias emerges which, according to epidemiological standards, could suggest that the observed associations are spurious. Further investigation using non-aggregated data is necessary for a definitive assessment of the results' generalizability.

Keywords: N-size Datasets, Oncology, Data Integrity, Data Reliability, COVID-19 Vaccination

1. Introduction

The safety profile of COVID-19 vaccination has increasingly been addressed as a multifaceted toxicological challenge, characterized by a plurality of potential adverse events. Despite extensive research, the scientific debate remains significantly open, with contrasting findings that sustain a complex and ongoing international discussion on the subject [1, 2].

In this context, recent observational research has utilized large-scale health administrative databases to investigate potential correlations between COVID-19 vaccination and the incidence of several diseases, including various forms of cancer. One such study [3] suggests a higher rate of new cancer cases among the vaccinated population compared to the unvaccinated in South Korea. While the magnitude of such datasets often implies a high degree of statistical power, the interpretability of the resulting associations is to be put in comparison with established national health benchmarks for a better comprehension and utilization of the resulting findings.

Drawing on previous preliminary studies [4, 5], the objective of our analysis is to verify the external consistency of the cohort utilized in [3] by comparing the study's internal metrics against official national statistics from South Korean benchmarks, specifically regarding crude incidence rates and demographic distributions. This analysis aims to quantify the extent to which the cohort reflects the oncological and demographic reality of the South Korean population, and whether potential discrepancies could influence the reported associations.

2. Master Data, Benchmarking Sources and Methods

Study [3] is a retrospective, cohort-based observational analysis spanning 2021-2023, drawing data from a South Korean National Health Insurance database and suggesting a higher rate of new cancer cases among the COVID-19 vaccinated population compared to the unvaccinated. Raw data for estimating the incidence metrics were extracted from Table S4 of the Supplementary Material.

The authors initiated the study with an initial South Korean cohort of 8,407,849 individuals. Following a 1:4 Propensity Score Matching (PSM) [6], the final study population consisted of 2,975,035 individuals (595,007 unvaccinated and 2,380,028 vaccinated), representing approximately 5.7% of South Korea's total population (51.7 million). The total number of cancer cases reported during the observation period was 12,133.

To evaluate the external consistency of the dataset, official 2022 statistics extracted from the South Korean Central Cancer Registries were utilized as the definitive gold standard [7-11]. Table 1 contrasts these national benchmarks with the specific metrics reported in the study cohort.

Table 1. Structural Comparison: National Benchmarks vs. Study Cohort

Category	Demographic Weight (<i>w</i>)	Participants (<i>N</i>)	Cancer Cases (<i>n</i>)	Crude Incidence Rate (per 10k)
National (Gold Standard 2022)				
Elderly (≥ 65)	18.00%	N/A	N/A	155.20
Young (< 65)	82.00%	N/A	N/A	33.03
National Total	100.00%	N/A	N/A	55.02
Study (Unvaccinated)				
Elderly (≥ 65)	12.15%	72,285	616	85.22
Young (< 65)	87.85%	522,722	1,373	26.27
Total Unvaccinated	100.00%	595,007	1,989	33.43
Study (Vaccinated)				
Elderly (≥ 65)	12.15%	289,140	3,283	113.54

Young (<65)	87.85%	2,090,888	6,861	32.81
<hr/>				
Total Vaccinated	100.00%	2,380,028	10,144	42.63

To compare the cohort with the population using the data of Table 1 above, we utilized three fundamental formulas:

First, the Crude Cancer Incidence Rate (CR). It determines the raw frequency of cancer cases within a specific group, normalized per 10,000 individuals to allow for direct comparison between different sample sizes:

$$CR = (Population\ at\ Risk / Number\ of\ Cases) \times 10,000 \quad (1).$$

Second, the Relative Demographic Deficit/Surplus (%). It measures the percentage deviation of the cohort's age distribution from the official national demographic architecture:

$$Rel.\ Deficit\ \% = ((Population\ \% - Cohort\ \%) - Population\ \%) \times 100 \quad (2).$$

Third and final, the Difference in Incidence (% Suppression). It quantifies the gap between the observed incidence rate in the study and the expected national reference rate:

$$Diff.\ \% = ((Reference\ CR - Cohort\ CR) / Reference\ CR) \times 100 \quad (3).$$

3. Results

We developed calculations to compute respectively: the total incidence, the demographic distribution and the group-specific incidence achieving the following results.

Applying Formula 1 to the total cohort (12,133 cases / 2,975,035 participants) yields a Raw Incidence Rate of 40.78 per 10,000. The difference compared to the national benchmark (55.02) is calculated using Formula 3 as follows:

$$\text{Difference} = ((40.78 - 55.02) / 55.02) \times 100 = -26.0\% \quad (4).$$

In essence, the cohort exhibits a 26% lower overall incidence compared to national figures.

Then we took into account the elderly population (≥ 65) which represents 12.15% of the study cohort (361,425 / 2,975,035). Applying Formula 2 to compare this with the national weight of 18.00% we get:

$$\text{Difference} = ((12.15\% - 18.00\%) / 18.00\%) \times 100 = -32.5\% \quad (5).$$

Clearly, the study cohort contains 32.5% fewer elderly individuals than the national reference population.

Finally, we focused on the the unvaccinated elderly subgroup (Unvaccinated ≥ 65), the reported CR is 85.22 (616 cases / 72,285 participants). Applying Formula 3 against the national benchmark (155.20) for this specific stratum we get:

$$\text{Difference} = ((85.22 - 155.20) / 155.20) \times 100 = -45.1\% \quad (6).$$

This puts in evidence that the unvaccinated elderly group in the study presents 45.1% fewer cancer cases than expected based on national statistics.

4. Discussion

The evidence we have provided through the results from Formulas 4-6 demonstrates a three-level structural divergence cohort-population. Specifically, the study is characterized by a -26.0% overall incidence gap, a -32.5% demographic under-representation of the high-risk elderly group, and a -45.1% divergence in the unvaccinated control group's incidence.

Based on these results, there is enough evidence to affirm that associations vaccine/cancer reported in [3] suffer from a massive selection bias. The observed increase in relative cancer risk could be a

result stemming from a structurally unrepresentative control group with a significantly suppressed baseline [12].

Standard epidemiological textbooks state that if significant selection biases affect a study, the resulting associations can be rightfully suspected of being spurious [12]. This study appears to be such a case. Regardless of whether these associations are ultimately proven spurious, they certainly cannot be considered generalizable to the broader South Korean population without further investigation [14].

5. Conclusion

The comparative analysis presented in this study highlights significant structural discrepancies between the cohort metrics in [3] and the official South Korean national benchmarks, specifically the -26.0% overall incidence gap, the -32.5% demographic under-representation of the elderly, and the -45.1% case suppression in the unvaccinated control group.

Even if this suggests the presence of a substantial selection bias, and standard epidemiological principles indicate that when a study is affected by significant selection biases the resulting associations may be rightfully suspected of being spurious, we do not intend to diminish the relevance of the original study. This is because we believe it should still be subject to further investigation and because, like many other independent researchers, we do not have access to the primary database required to perform exhaustive counter-analyses.

Therefore, until proven otherwise, we are not disputing the statistical association found in that study, which correlates COVID-19 vaccination with a higher number of new cancer cases compared to the non-vaccinated population. What we do want is to highlight the discrepancies arising from a comparison with national benchmarks, which suggest the presence of a massive selection bias. A solution to this methodological dilemma is necessary: to ensure scientific integrity and public trust, such databases must be made public and accessible to the independent research community. Only through open access can researchers carry out in-depth, transparent analyses from every possible perspective to confirm or question these associations.

For the completeness of this scientific record, it is worth reminding that similar questionable associations between COVID-19 vaccinations and other SAEs (Serious Adverse Effects) drawn by the same dataset scrutinized in this note were discussed in recently published studies by the same author of this note [15-17].

Declarations

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Data Availability Statement: The data presented here is either included directly or was extracted from the referenced documents. All calculations are easily reproducible based on the definitions provided

Ethics approval and consent to participate: This study uses publicly available, aggregated data that contains no private information. Therefore, ethical approval is not required

Conflicts of Interest: The author declares no competing interests

Authors' Contribution: MR is the the single author of this manuscript. He conceived, wrote, revised and approved it.

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